

Original Research

The Role of IGAD in Drought Response in the Horn of Africa

Merhawi Yemane^{1*}, Iris Borowy¹,

¹ College of Liberal Arts, Shanghai University, No. 99 Shangda Road, Baoshan District, Shanghai, 200444, China

Article history:

Received: 01 November 2025

Accepted: 18 November 2025

Published Online: 30 November 2025

*Correspondence:

Merhawi Yemane, College of liberal Arts, Shanghai University, No. 99 Shangda Road, Baoshan District, Shanghai, 200444, China

How to cite this article:

Merhawi Yemane, Iris Borowy (2025) The Role of IGAD in Drought Response in the Horn of Africa, *North American Academic Research*, 8(11), 312-323. doi: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19057498>

Publisher's Note: NAAR stays neutral about jurisdictional claims in published maps/image and institutional affiliations. **Copyright:** ©2025 by the authors. Author(s) are fully responsible for the text, figure, data in this manuscript submitted for possible open access publication under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>)

Abstract

For several decades, the region has been affected by the consequences of climate change with effects on the socioeconomic, political and security aspects in general and on the pastoralist (agriculture and livestock) mode of life in particular. This reliance on arid areas makes local economies and communities vulnerable to drought. Recurrent droughts impair food production, disrupts markets, depletes pastures and, at its worst, leads to a large number of fatalities among people and animals, and increased violence. This development has contradictory effect on regional security. And, the shared physical threats and challenges brought on by climate change present a potential rallying point for regional cooperation in which IGAD stands to coordinate and tackle the existing challenges. On the other hand, competition for access to these few natural resources is also a major factor igniting conflicts and instability in the region. To tackle this problem, IGAD was set up in 1986 with narrow mandate of tackling drought and other environmental issues. This research project has employed both qualitative and quantitative data analysis method, while using scholarly literature to trace the consequences of climate change, and the effort made by IGAD.

Keywords: Horn of Africa, IGAD, CEWARN, Drought, Pastoralism

Introduction

Often at the edge of human existence, pastoralism is characterized by a finely tuned symbiotic relationship between the local ecology, animals, and people in areas with few resources as well as high variability. For 100 to 200 million pastoralists worldwide, the practice of extensive grazing of rangelands—which make up around 25% of the planet's geographical area—forms a vital part of their economic and cultural lives (Gebrehiwot, 2012).

The Horn of Africa comprises a land area of 5.2. million km. Its topography includes lowlands, highlands as well as lowland-highlands transition zones, all of which are significant in different ways. Lowland areas are primarily defined by pastoralist modes of production, where raising cattle is the main economic activity, whereas highlands are the home sources of rivers as well as areas of established agriculture. The lowland-highland interaction zones have created a

dynamic shift in natural resources, population migrations, and human life-sustaining activities. This situation led to substantial product trade as well as shared usage of natural resources, however, during (frequent) times of resource scarcity and in the absence of established guidelines for resource sharing, these exchanges have not always been amicable (Tafesse, 2009).

The climate of the Horn of Africa region has been shaped by its location on the equator, its high elevation and the westerly monsoon winds that originate in the Ethiopian Highlands. People in these countries often identify two different seasons of precipitation: the "short rains" which extend from October to December, while the "long rains" persist from March to May. Ethiopia has semi-arid and dry features, whereas Somalia, Djibouti and Eritrea primarily have humid and arid climates. Kenya, on the other hand, is mostly known for its dry climate. Rangeland farming, small-scale agriculture, dairy product and milk production manufacturing, and pastoralism and agropastoralism are the main livelihood in the region (Ahmed, Shahid, and Mohammed, 2024). This research paper explores consequences of environmental degradation in human and animal population in the region, and at the same time also explores the efforts made by IGAD to tackle the consequences of environmental degradation in the Horn of Africa.

1. Pastoralism and the Consequences of Environmental Degradation

The Horn of Africa has a population of about 230 million people, made up of many ethnic and linguistic groups, whose histories have been marked by their position at the intersection of several commerce and migration routes. For centuries, agriculture has remained the main sources of the economy and livelihood of the people in the region. For-example, the foundation of Somalia's livelihood and economy has remained the agricultural sector. In the early 2020s, it accounted for 93% of the Somalia's exports, 65% of the Gross Domestic Products, and created an employment for 65% of Somalis. Notably, Somalia continued to practice traditional ways of livestock keeping as well as agricultural cultivation (Abdimalik and Jama, 2023).

Overall, crop production and livestock raising has formed the foundation for food supply, revenue, and employment for more than 80% of the population in the region. Their lives are made difficult by the fact that they live in a very dry region. Less than 600 mm of rainfall falls yearly on the arid as well as semi-arid regions that make up about 70% of the region and of the entire land area, 7% is devoted to agriculture, 19% to forests, and 28% to permanent pasture (Nega, 2020). The remaining 46% of the land is marginal or relatively unproductive and only suitable for pastoralism. Consequently, nomadic pastoralism plays an important role in the socio-economic setup of these countries, and this is especially true for Somalia and Ethiopia as well as Sudan, which has the greatest percentage of pastoralists worldwide (Kennedy, 2001). But also in Djibouti, a third of the population are pastoralists, and even in relatively prosperous Kenya, 80% of the land mass is made up of semi-arid and arid territory, which supports half of the nation's livestock and 25% of its population. Overall, these areas contribute 20 to 30 % to the region's GDP. At the local level, livestock accounted up to 70% of all monetary income (Kennedy, 2001).

Meanwhile, due to geography and regional climatic pattern, the region's temperature and annual precipitation vary significantly. Inland regions are characterized by arid as well as semi-arid conditions, notwithstanding the tropical environment of coastal areas. Climates range from Somalia's extremely arid environment, which receives 100 to 500 mm of rainfall annually, Ethiopia experiences a little more though still very limited 500 to 2200 mm of precipitation on average each year. Despite the region's aridity agriculture remained essential to the local economy (Ahmed, Mohammed, and Shamsuddin, 2004).

Figure 1: Arable land (% of Arable area)

Source : <https://data.worldbank.org/indicator/AG.LND.ARBL.ZS?end=2002&locations=ET-SO-SD-ER-DJ-KE-UG>

Around 70% of the region is arid and semi-arid, where very low percentage of its total area suitable for crop cultivation. And according to the give above data in 2010, only 10.6% of the total land of the region was arable, while, in 2008, the total arable land of Uganda, Ethiopia and Kenya was 32.3%, 12% and 9% respectively, while in Eritrea, Somalia and Djibouti was 5.5 %, 1.7% and 0.1% respectively (Figure 1).

Figure 2: forest area (% of land area)

Source: World Bank national accounts data, and OECD National Accounts data files:

<https://data.worldbank.org/indicator/AG.LND.FRST.ZS?end=2002&locations=ET-SO-SD-ER-DJ-KE-UG>

Since several decades, the Horn of Africa was one of the most droughts affected region. And the main factors that caused drought were; environmental degradation, deforestation and climate change. In 1960s and 1970s, out of the total land area, 19% was covered by forestry area, which later began to decline due to overgrazing, cleaning the area for farming, using the fire wood as a source of energy, climate change etc. Figure 7 shows that, in Ethiopia, out of total land area, 19% of it was covered by forestry, while in Somalia and Kenya 12.8 % and 6.8 % respectively in 1993. However, these percentage further declined after two decades. In Ethiopia it declined to 15.8 %, while in Somalia and Kenya to 10.8% and 6.4 % respectively in 2010. Consequently, such fast deforestation exposed the region for consecutive drought, which affected the human (conflicts for pasture and water among different pastoralists communities, human death, migration) and animal population of the region (Figure 2).

Figure 3: Livestock production index (2014-2016=100)

Source: World Bank national accounts data, and OECD National Accounts data files: <https://data.worldbank.org/indicator/NY.GDP.MKTP.KD.ZG?end=2002&locations=ET-SO-SD->

In considering the topographic and climatic condition of the region, Pastoralism and livestock were two faces of the same coin in the Horn of Africa, where majority of livelihood of the people in Somalia, Eritrea, Djibouti, Sudan, and Ethiopia depended on. Figure 8 shows that, in 1995, the livestock production in Djibouti was 99.1 %, while in Somalia and Eritrea 89.5% and 59.2% respectively. However, in Uganda and Ethiopia the number was slightly low, 45.8% and 45.2 % respectively because the population engaged more on crop production (settled agriculturalists). Meanwhile, due to the failure of governments of the region to explore other livelihood conditions such as manufacturing, still the mode of life depended on livestock production and at the same time also exposed the region for further environmental degradation. Furthermore, Figure 3 further shows that, in 2004, Djibouti livestock production was 105.9 %, while in Somalia and Eritrea 103.6% and 83.8% respectively (Figure 3).

This reliance on arid areas made local economies and communities vulnerable to drought. Over history, recurrent droughts had impaired food production, depleted pastures, disrupted markets, and, at its worst, led to a large number of fatalities among people and animals. In addition, droughts had caused increased migration from rural to urban regions, adding to pressure on the world's already dwindling food supply. Due to competition for the limited resources, herders were frequently compelled to find alternate sources of food and water for their livestock (Kennedy, 2001, p.2). Overall, this means that heavy environmental degradation could be a source of ethnic tensions, when ethnic groups with different socioeconomical traditions share a sensitive eco-region (Gunther Bachler,1995).

In the past three decades, there have been six significant drought spells on the African continent. Moreover, the latest droughts in Ethiopia, Kenya, and Somalia caused fatalities as well as a 60–70% decrease in the number of cattle in some regions (Kennedy, 2001). Similarly, famine struck Somalia in 2011 due to a severe drought—at the time, the worst in 60 years—and substantial access problems, while a severe drought over the region resulted in up to 260 000 deaths, half of them children (FAO, 2022).

Already scarce, water resources are being strained by rising temperatures, rapid population expansion, and rising migration. As a result of climate change and accompanying environmental shocks, the area has become increasingly vulnerable to drought, and this has led to poverty, mass migration, biodiversity loss, and increased violence. In addition, numerous farmers and herders have lost their jobs, and numerous families' incomes have been drastically cut to the point where they must now look for shelter in urban areas. Furthermore, climate change is expected to cause the Horn region to undergo substantial changes in rainfall and temperatures, which will likely make the area's water insecurity worse (Yeboua and Cilliers, 2021).

For several decades, the region has been affected by the consequences of climate change with effects on the socioeconomic, political and security aspects in general and on the pastoralist (agriculture and livestock) mode of life in particular. This development has contradictory effect on regional security. And, the shared physical threats and challenges brought on by climate change present a potential rallying point for regional cooperation in which IGAD stands to coordinate and tackle the existing challenges (Nega, 2020). On the other hand, competition for access to these few natural resources is also a major factor igniting conflicts and instability in the area (Yeboua and Cilliers, 2021).

The diminishing resource base damages long-standing social structures and fosters severe competition. In the absence of an enabling social environment and ingrained processes that encourage discussion between different identities, value systems, and belief systems competition for resources has been resulted in violent conflicts. And that risk increases as resources are limited and the population is expanding quickly, creating a volatile social environment that encourages group conflict (Bereketeab, 2018).

The consequences of changing weather patterns on crops and cattle have exacerbated socio-economic pressures on farmers and herders. Moreover, the great reliance on natural resources for food and money gives rise to complaints that lead to territorial tensions and potential confrontations. Additionally, declining living standards encourage individuals to join armed organizations and use violence to end regional issues. One study investigating the link between local differences in weather shocks and hostilities in North as well as South Sudan between 1997 and 2009 discovered that temperature fluctuations have a significant impact on the chance of violence (Solomon, 2018). Other conflicts show similar patterns.

For several decades, the lack of water has been a major source of conflict between and among communities in the pastoralist nomadic societies of Somalia. According to research commissioned by the Ministry of Planning in Somalia in collaboration with development partners, food insecurity and water shortages play a substantial role in rural conflict, child malnutrition, and water-borne illness in the nation. And, the primary water supplies for Somalia are the Jubba and Shebelle rivers, both of which originate in Ethiopia (Yeboua and Cilliers, 2021).

Improving Somalia's water security requires both a national water policy to control and manage internal water resources and a bilateral agreement between Somalia and Ethiopia on the shared waters of the two rivers. In addition, overgrazing of the Somali bush in Somalia has resulted in the desertification of grazing fields, as well as hunger and drought in the past. Additionally, unlike earlier, the diverse pastoralist communities are unable to traverse such enormous distances: Conflicts between them have gotten worse as competition for grazing grounds and water has increased (Yeboua and Cilliers, 2021).

Conflicts over water and pasture have been a recurring source of discord among lineage groupings and clans in Africa in general and in the region in particular. Often, force was the only tool that could be used to support such assertions, and it was a constant in nomadic life. Moreover, the protracted crisis and persistent confrontations between Somali clans have weakened traditional methods of conflict management, making it harder to keep violence under control. In addition, the Somali clan system, in other words, is centripetal and centrifugal, at the same time bringing the Somalis into a powerful social web of kinship affinity and cultural cohesion while putting them against one another in opposing clan interests (Samatar, Abdi Ismail and Machak, 2006).

As a case in point, long-running conflicts between the Ishaq clans in Ethiopia and Ogaden Somalis have been affected by changing climate, as environmental conditions in northern Somalia caused many Ishaq to move into the Ogaden. As the demand for meat, exported to the Middle East increased during the ensuing decades, animal populations soared, further increasing environmental stressors. Furthermore, the issue contributed to the war between Ethiopia and Somalia in 1977–1978, and the conflict between the two major clan families continues to have an impact on internal politics in Somalia to this day. Also, unusually high temperatures and droughts force herders to sell more sheep than usual (Kumar, Ajim, and Ahmad, 2020). Economic price shocks caused by an overabundance of low-quality animals made the people more vulnerable both to recruitment by armed groups and to livestock raids (Kumar, Ajim, and Ahmad, 2020). It has been estimated, that an increase in drought intensity and length by one standard deviation increases the chance of violence in Somalia by 62% (Solomon, 2018).

Another study made on climate-conflict relationship for East Africa from 1990-2009 revealed that wetter deviations from the precipitation norms decreased the risk of violence, while drier and normal periods showed no effects, but significantly warmer than normal temperatures did. In academia, this correlation between the environment and conflict

has become more widely acknowledged. For-example, according to Homer-Dixon's conflict causality model, which correlated the environment and conflict, failed states were more susceptible to environmental stress and experienced four basic causally connected effects: decreased agricultural output, an economic crisis, civil unrest, as well as population displacement (Solomon, 2018).

The degree to which nomadic pastoralism is at odds with modern states and fixed borders is also borne out by conflicts in the Lake Turkana area, near the border between Ethiopia and Kenya where pastoralists in south Turkana have traditionally "traveled 10-15 times each year in search of patchy rainfall zones and pockets of high-potential rangelands for their livestock," (Meyer, Bond, and Bond, 2007). These Turkana cross into southern Ethiopia on occasion in search of water and pasture. Their behavior is in line with findings of the Inter-governmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) 2001 Report, which predicted that average changes in resource allocation might alter migration, increasing the risks of tension and conflict (Meyer, Bond, and Bond, 2007). Indeed, in a latest field research, pastoralists in the Cluster identified competition for grazing space and water as the single most significant structural reason for conflict (Meyer, Bond, and Bond, 2007).

Similarly, several decades of conflict with racial and environmental roots led to near-anarchy in Sudan at Darfur in the late 1980s and early 1990s. Historically, when sedentary African communities harvested their crops, northwestern Arab pastoralists moved southward along their migration routes into these regions. Responding to changing weather conditions, the Arab pastoralists began migrating their livestock considerably earlier in search of pasture and water because of droughts as well as expanding desertification, frequently ruining the unharvested fields of the African farmers. The contention and conflict between these two communities remained imminent and intensified than any time before (Isaac and Targowski, 2015).

The drought-induced famines also had an effect on political leadership in the area. For example, the prolonged drought and famine in Ethiopia in the 1970s and 80s facilitated the deposition of Emperor Haile Selassie, and the defeat of Derg (a military regime which ruled Ethiopia from 1974-1991) in 1974 and 1991 respectively. To escape from the ongoing crises, the Derg regime introduced land reform, where land was redistributed to peasants. The land policy reform did not succeed since it interrupted the traditional agriculture system and the productive capacity, and eventually, it led to nationwide hunger, which contributed to the defeat and end of the regime in 1991 (Henze, 1991).

2. The Motive Behind Formation of IGAD

Following several years of drought in the region in the late 1970s and 1980s, especially devastating droughts and famines in Ethiopia and Somalia in 1984 and 1985, the UN issued resolution 35/90 in 1980 recommending that Governments of the drought-stricken countries of the region should consider the establishment of an intergovernmental body with the responsibility for coordinating and supporting the countries' efforts to combat the effects of drought and other natural disasters and to deal with the problem of medium-term and long-term recovery and rehabilitation (Byiers, 2017). The task of overseeing this procedure was assigned to the UN Environment Program (UNEP) (Byiers, 2017). Hence, the Inter-Governmental Authority against Drought and Desertification (IGADD) was established in 1986 with the participation of the governments of six nations: Ethiopia, Djibouti, Kenya, Somalia, Sudan, and Uganda. IGAD's organizational name gave no indication that it had any political aspirations for deeper regional integration, and its mandate was limited to environmental protection, food security, and resource management. Meanwhile, the new institution received strong backing from the European Union, which highlighted its ability to serve as a development agency (Healy, 2001).

Figure 1: Map of IGAD's member countries

Source : <https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Badal-Ahmed-Hassan>

The origins of IGAD thus lie in the intertwined environmental and security conditions of the area.

The primary driving force behind the creation of IGADD was to address the consequences of natural disasters like drought and flooding, from which the area had long suffered. In 1996, when it became clear that this limited mandate was unable to meet the significant shared difficulties the area faced, the Intergovernmental Authority on Drought and Development (IGADD) was forced to change its name to Intergovernmental Authority on Development (IGAD) with a more extended mandate (Weldesellassie, 2011).

IGAD's organizational structures represent its intergovernmental nature and the reality in the ground. Similar to any other intergovernmental organizations, important decisions are taken by the IGAD Heads of State and Government, often known as the IGAD Summit, which convenes at least once a year. The second body, the Council of Ministers, is made up of the foreign ministers and one additional focal minister chosen by each member state (Dersso, 2014). During its biannual sessions, this body is in charge of establishing policy and approving the work schedule and annual budget of the secretariat. In addition, a Committee of Ambassadors, made up of ambassadors from IGAD member states who are accredited to the IGAD headquarters in Djibouti, is a permanent policymaking body that oversees the IGAD secretariat's work (Dersso, 2014).

The IGAD secretariat is the organization's executive body, and it is charged with assisting member states in developing regional projects in priority regions, facilitating the coordination and harmonization of development policies, mobilizing funding to carry out regional projects and programs authorized by the council, and strengthening the national infrastructures required for their implementation. Furthermore, the secretariat embraced six main functional departments: Agriculture and environment, Economic Cooperation and Regional Integration, Health and Social Development, Peace and Security, Administration and finance, and Planning Coordination and Partnerships, while the executive secretary serves as the secretariat's chief administrative officer (Dersso, 2014).

IGAD's Organisational Structure

Organizational Structure of IGAD

Source: <https://www.google.co.in/url?sa=i&url=https%3A%2F%2Fslideplayer.com%2Fslide%2F8954009%2F&psig=AOvVaw0yHTgdc7K5O6fSUI83u5tU&ust=1752462757922000&source=images&>

These changes regarding IGAD did not happen in a political vacuum. Many regional and international circumstances prompted and pushed IGAD to expand its scope and mandate beyond addressing drought. Thereby, it must be seen as one of several initiatives taken to promote African regional collaboration. For instance, several initiatives, ranging from specific to broad, have been taken to achieve the Africa Agenda 2063, an agenda approved in 2013 by the African Union which aimed to promote and guide Africa toward political and economic integration. In doing so, in June 1991, the Abuja Treaty established the African Economic Community (AEC), setting the stage for the creation of a single economic union for all of Africa.

In addition to emphasizing political stability as a crucial element for development in the post-Cold War era, the Abuja Treaty accorded special recognition to the role that the existing regional economic communities (RECs) played for establishing the AEC. Three years later, the UN Convention to Combat Desertification was adopted in Paris, which upgraded the challenges of drought and desertification on the international agenda. Furthermore, the region's political dynamism from war to peace was also a major driving force for economic cooperation and regional integration (Weldesellassie, 2011). The end of the long and bloody war between Eritrea and Ethiopia (1961-91), which finally led to Eritrean independence propelled the region toward peace and collaboration, and Eritrea and Ethiopia experienced economic integration for nearly a decade (Weldesellassie, 2011).

The end of Cold War signaled new political configuration, where old regimes in Ethiopia and Somalia gave way for new regime and new leadership, giving independence of Eritrea in 1991. This situation increased the willingness of nations to cooperate, which also showed positive results with regard to the Sudan peace process. Collectively, these changes favored the creation of a regional organization with a broader scope (Byiers, 2016). Thus, the political dynamism of the Horn of Africa in the early 1990s was the main pushing factor for the revitalization of IGADD. Part of this picture was the degree, to which the new rulers of Ethiopia and Eritrea established their control rapidly and were eager to take advantage of the chances for regional collaboration. Soon, they began reviving IGADD with a much more expansive mandate that included regional security. Moreover, the new generation of leaders Presidents Yoweri Museveni Uganda, Meles Zenawi Ethiopia, and Issayas Afwerki (Eritrea had a radical vibe and all achieved military success against the established order, and they were proud to have toppled oppressive regimes (Healy, 2011).

3. IGAD and Its Climate Related Institutions

One of the main responsibilities of IGAD is to ensure the protection and sustainable use of the natural and physical environment. Because of the extensive environmental degradation, the area has been dealing with for many years,

IGAD's attention has been drawn particularly to the need to safeguard the natural environment and promote sustainable resource use. As a result of the Regional Strategy to Combat Desertification and the Forum on Environmental Protection held in Nairobi in 1990, IGAD launched the Environment Assessment for Sustainable Environment Management as one of its initiatives. And, its purpose was to assist national initiatives and provide monitoring capacity and analysis of environmental change processes and their effects on ecosystems and regional development (Dersso, 2014).

For the political side of development, IGAD created the Conflict Early Warning and Response Mechanism (CEWARN) as part of the IGAD Peace and Security Division (Dersso, 2014, p. 8). Its basis was the Protocol on the Establishment of a Conflict Early Warning and Response Mechanism (CEWARN) for IGAD Member States, which was signed on 9 January 2002 and came into effect in 2003 after being ratified by the necessary majority of IGAD member states. In addition, the IGAD sub-regional operational framework for conflict early warning and response was formalized with a mandate to gather, receive, and share information about possible violent conflicts as well as their emergence and development (Weldesellassie, 2011).

The establishment and operation of CEWARN have been one of IGAD's most important accomplishments in the areas of peace and security, where the regional early warning units, or CEWARUs, located in each IGAD member state cooperate with the CEWARN headquarter in Addis Abeba (Dersso, 2014). Initially, the scope of CEWARN activities was narrow, concentrated on disputes involving pastoralists and associated issues in the region of Karamoja clusters, a cross-border area composed of southwest Ethiopia, Northern Kenya, Southeast South Sudan and Northern Uganda which is inhabited by 13 groups of pastoralists and agro-pastoralists. And, clearly, the IGAD governments were only willing to work on non-intrusive, politically non-sensitive problems in the early phases of the formation of CEWARN (Dersso, 2014).

As explained, pastoralists have been in constant movement from one country to another, causing conflicts on different sides of the borders, while progress has been very limited and, by some accounts, the problem is actually getting worse. How to gather and handle data in a situation in which member states lack trust in one another, and how to maintain the political will for cooperation remain unresolved problems. Also, there are issues with finances and a lack of coordination and communication between CEWARN and national CEWARN units. In addition to the existing challenges, CEWARN has called for member states to cooperate in a timely and transparent manner and keep an open flow of information. However, the current political environment is unfavorable, making execution only partially successful. And, due to lack of trust, each member state is only permitted to access the data that are under its own Conflict Early Warning and Responses Mechanism Unite (CEWARU) supervision (Weldesellassie, 2011). Therefore, it was challenging to imagine how the mechanism might function over the long term without the joint operations of the IGAD Secretariat in Djibouti as well as the CEWARN office in Addis Abeba. In addition to having a complicated process, the mechanism lacks clear definitions of what constitutes an early intervention or general preventive response (Weldesellassie, 2011).

The CEWARN mechanism has a primarily short-term goal of detecting when and where conflicts may arise and of avoiding their outbreak by taking appropriate action. This is in addition to its temporary restriction to cross-border pastoral conflict. It has not yet established a long-term goal nor has it addressed the wider aspects of security within a conflict prevention approach that concentrates on resolving the causes of the conflict (such as democratization and the protection of human rights). Furthermore, when there are high tensions, a lack of confidence, and unsolved issues between member nations, make it difficult to cooperate on conflict prevention, improving collaboration, and cooperative activities (Weldesellassie, 2011).

Meanwhile, parts of the Horn of Africa experienced some of the worst droughts in recorded history between 2010 and 2011. As a result, Heads of State and Government from IGAD and the East African Community (EAC) came together to support a more proactive, regional, and all-encompassing strategy to end drought emergencies in the area. Furthermore, the IGAD Drought Disaster Resilience and Sustainability Initiative (IDDRSI) was established in 2011 at a summit with the goal of operationalizing the drought resilience agenda on ending drought catastrophes in the region's arid and semi-arid lands. In addition, a Regional Programming Plan was created by the IGAD Secretariat after consultation with member states, development partners, and other stakeholders, including non-state actors, in order to organize and mobilize resources around all the processes (Byiers, 2017).

These new mechanisms gave IGAD a clear mandate to coordinate drought resilience efforts across the region, encourage better cooperation amongst the many stakeholders, and secure funding for long-term initiatives. Moreover, IDDRSI's seven top intervention priorities span all four pillars of the organization's overarching strategy. IDDRSI also compiles

in a single policy document the goals, values, strategies, and resources required to increase resilience in the IGAD region (Bizzotto, 2018).

In a surprisingly short amount of time, IDDRSI was able to successfully mobilize resources and rally high level support, and from 2013 onward, about USD 1 billion were raised and committed as funding for the execution of IDDRSI initiatives in various nations. In addition, the IGAD Heads of State Summits in Nairobi (2011) and Kampala (2014) successfully served as forums for Member States to reaffirm their dedication to the IDDRSI as a coordinated regional strategy to increase the drought resilience of vulnerable populations (Samatar, Abdi Ismail and Machaka, 2006).

4. IGAD and the Role of International Partners

The standard of living in Horn of Africa region would have deteriorated considerably more than it did in the 1980s without both emergency relief and increases in development aid. Nearly all of this aid came from international lending organizations and the foreign aid programs of Western nations, especially from the European Union. In comparison to numerous Western European nations, the United States made a lower contribution, while Arab states that are rich in oil also provided support to Somalia and Sudan (Henze, 1991). Meanwhile, the contribution of Soviet Bloc countries has been negligible, even to Ethiopia, a country with which they were allied. Overall, for the last three decades most of the substantial technical and materials aid has been granted from Western countries and its NGO (Henze, 1991).

This situation is also reflected in the funding of IGAD. Around 10% of the IGAD budget, or about USD 115 million on average each year, has been obtained through contributions from member states, while the remainder of the IGAD budget has been provided by the development partners. For example, between 2009 and 2012, the average international partner contribution to IGAD was 34.5% from individual EU member states and 27.5% from EU institutions. In addition, the World Bank contributed 21% of this total, with the remaining funds coming from USAID (8%), the UN (3%), the African Development Bank (1%), Canada (1%), Norway (1%), and 3% through the Joint Financing Arrangement (Byiers, 2016).

International funders have pledged development assistance for projects in eight nations aimed at boosting economies and reducing war and starvation in the unstable region. Leaders of global and regional organizations launched a historic tour to the Horn of Africa to offer political support and significant new financial support for countries in the region totaling more than \$8 billion over the coming few years. Furthermore, the African Union (AU), the European Union (EU), the African Development Bank (AfDB), and the Intergovernmental Agency for Development (IGAD) are joining forces to promote stability and development in the Horn of Africa. In addition, the World Bank made a huge new financial pledge of \$1.8 billion for cross-border activity in a Horn of Africa Project that designed to reduce environmental degradation and improve economic development and opportunity, decrease poverty, and stimulate commercial activity. In addition, the EU offered a total of \$3.7 billion in assistance for the countries until 2020, with around 10% going to cross-border operations which primarily focus on the Initiative's three pillars: enhancing growth, decreasing poverty by building resilience, and generating economic opportunities (World Bank – Africa Research Bulletin: Policy and Practice).

In 2009, Ethiopia and the World Bank signed an agreement for a \$80 million grant to support the completion of the second phase of the agricultural growth project (AGP II). Also, the bank authorized International Development Association (IDA) assistance to assist the government in increasing agricultural productivity and improving market access for smallholder farmers. In addition, AGPII has aided in increasing access to agricultural services for almost 1.4 million smallholder farmers, 37% of whom are women. Furthermore, it has also effectively promoted over 254 innovative agricultural technologies, many of which have a major influence on crop productivity, as well as climate-smart treatments (FANA 24/9). In addition to the AGP 2, as part of its effort to maximize crop production, the Ethiopian government also initiated Irrigation Growth Project 1 (IGP 1).

Beyond IDDRSI, the development partners that were most engaged in the IGAD region's cross-border zones were the United States, United Kingdom Germany, the United Nations, the World Bank, FAO, and the African Development Bank. Furthermore, the IGAD Partners' Forum (IPF) and the Global Alliance for Action on Drought Resilience and Growth in the Horn of Africa were two donor organizations that supported alignment, coordination as well as harmonization efforts in the region. And, as a part of IGAD's formal governance framework, the IPF was established in 1997 (Bizzotto, 2018). The Global Alliance is a donor organization that was established in 2012 to bring the leadership of numerous international development partners together around fresh approaches to combining humanitarian aid with development support to create long-term resilience, it includes IGAD and is headed by USAID (Bizzotto, 2018).

5. Challenges

However, while the factors mentioned above fostered its creation and early work, other circumstances impeded easy success (Bizzotto, 2018). The collapse of Somalia after prolonged civil war, the continued civil war in Sudan, and other conflicts all made cooperation difficult. Moreover, effective implementation of IGAD decision were hampered by a lack of reliable funding and by remaining tensions between national interest and a regional approach, where member countries prioritize their national interest over their regional interest (Bizzotto, 2018).

Meanwhile, Somalia has been a classical example of a failed state since the 1990s. Although many factors contributed to its failure, the pastoralist clan nature of its society was one of the causes. Pastoralist clan conflicts over who controls water, land, and pasture has been the source of conflicts for centuries, even before colonialism arrived. Disturbed social harmony among societies was common. Furthermore, the negative legacy of colonialism, as Somalis have been divided in to four Horn of Africa countries, also contributed to state failure (Burgess, 2009).

Continued environmental degradation have remained ongoing challenges for several decades in the region, exacerbating the competition and struggle about the control of water holes and grassland. In addition, pastoralists engaged on continues conflict due to shortage of resources caused by climate change. Moreover, the raiding of cattle and other livestock was common phenomena among the pastoralists who lived in the cross border. For example, due to desertification, and resources scarcity, Oromo, and Somalis pastoralists have fought for several decades, which later undermine the state integrity in Ethiopia (Burgess, 2009).

Conclusion

Agriculture remained the foundation for food supply, a source of income as well as employment for more than 80% of the population in the region. However, their livelihood is made difficult by the fact that they live in a very dry region. Less than 600 mm of rainfall falls yearly on the arid and semi-arid territories that make up about 70% of the region. Therefore, the entire Horn of Africa region vulnerable to drought. Recurrent droughts impair food production, deplete pastures, disrupt markets, and, at their worst, lead to a large number of fatalities among people and animals, and increased violence.

This study examines pastoralism and the consequences of environmental degradation in the Horn of Africa Region. The result indicated that IGAD was set up as a result of environmental degradation and its consequences to animal population as well as human being. Therefore, to tackle the constant environmental related crises, IGAD established institutions such as CEWRAN and IDDRSI to share information between pastoralist and to avoid or minimize potential conflicts between pastoralist, which have been growing due to environmental degradation.

The establishment and operation of CEWARN have been one of IGAD's most important accomplishments in the areas of peace and security, where the regional early warning units, or CEWARUs, located in each IGAD member state cooperate with CEWARN, headquartered in Addis Ababa. These mechanisms are essential since 70% of the Horn of Africa is arid and semi-arid, where low parts of its total area suitable for crop cultivation. According to the research made in 2010 only 10.6% of the total land of the region was arable.

While a very positive and promising development, IGAD is not yet a self-sustaining institution.

All in all, IGAD as a regional organization as well as its environmental related institutions (IDDRSI and CEWARN) would not be work and operationalize without the assistance of development partners of Western nations, especially from European Economic Union, where most of the IGAD's budget comes from. In the long run, therefore, IGAD member countries must find the political will and economic resources to take full responsibility of their regional organization.

Author Contributions: At first page.

Approval: All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

Funding: This research received no external funding.

Institutional Review Board Statement: Not applicable.

Informed Consent Statement: Not applicable.

Data Availability Statement: Not applicable

Acknowledgments: Mentioned.

Conflicts of Interest: The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Acknowledgment

I would also like to express my gratitude to the shanghai university for the unwavering support and commitment to creating an environment conducive to learning, providing resources and personal growth.

Lists of Abbreviations

AGP	Agricultural growth project
AU	African Union
AFDB	African Development Bank
CEWARN	Conflict Early Warning and Response Mechanism
CEWARU	Conflict Early Warning and Response Mechanism Unite
EU	European Union
IGADD	Intergovernmental Authority for Drought and Development
IGAD	Intergovernmental Authority for Development
IPF	IGAD Partners' Forum
IDDRSI	IGAD Drought Disaster Resilience and Sustainability Initiative
IGP	Irrigation Growth Project
UNEP	United Nations Environment Program

References

IMF and World Bank Documents

[1] IMF. *Eritrea: Recent Economic Developments*. IMF Staff Country Reports 95, no. 4. Washington, D.C.: 1995.

<https://doi.org/10.5089/9781451811919.002>.

[2] IMF Eritrea: Recent Economic Developments. IMF Staff Country Report No. 96/66. Washington, D.C: IMF: 1996.

[https://review4.in/rw2.php?q=MF.%20\(1996\).%20Eritrea:%20Recent%20economic%20developments%20\(IMF%20Staff%20Country%20Report%20No.%2096/66\).%20Washington.%20D.C.%20IMF](https://review4.in/rw2.php?q=MF.%20(1996).%20Eritrea:%20Recent%20economic%20developments%20(IMF%20Staff%20Country%20Report%20No.%2096/66).%20Washington.%20D.C.%20IMF).

[3] IMF. *Eritrea: Selected Issues* IMF Staff Country Report No. 97/88. Washington, D.C: IMF: 1997.

<https://www.google.com/url?client=internal-element>

[cse&cx=d44d6207601c75cca&q=https://www.imf.org/external/pubs/ft/scr/1997/cr9788.pdf&sa=U&ved=2ahUKEwjL_4ovuGNAXUU4zQHHTHoOLQQFnoECAyQAQ&usg=AOvVaw19IPiUqRsyT7d14mFFDMef&fexp=72986053,72986052](https://www.imf.org/external/pubs/ft/scr/1997/cr9788.pdf)

[4] World bank national accounts data, and OECD National Accounts data files:

<https://data.worldbank.org/indicator/NY.GDP.MKTP.KD.ZG?end=2002&locations=ET-SO-SD->

ER&start=1979&view=chart#:~:text=World%20Bank%20national%20accounts%20data%2C%20and%20OECD%20National%20Accounts%20data%20files).

Books and Articles

- [1] Abdelwahab, El- Affendi, "The Impasse in the IGAD Peace Process for Sudan: the limits of Regional Peacemaking," *Africa Affairs*, (2001). Vol.100, No.401 (2001):581-99. <http://www.jstor.org/stable/3518702>.
- [2] Abdi, Ali I and Edris H. Seid. Assessment of Economic Integration in IGAD. The Horn Economic and Social Policy Institute (HESPI),2013: 31.URL <http://www.hespi.org/>.
- [3] Asfaw, Gudeta Kebede. "The Crucial Role of IGAD in the Horn of Africa" *International Journal of African and Asian Studies* Vol.38, 2017 *International Journal of African and Asian Studies* (2017):1-10. ISSN 2409-6938. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/337657664>
- [4] A.I. Samatar and Machaka. "Conflict and Peace in the Horn of Africa: A Regional Approach", in *In Quest for a Culture of Peace in the IGAD Region.* Nairobi, 2006.
- [5] Alasow, Ahmed Abdiaziz, Mohammed Magdy Hamed, and Shamsuddin Shahid. "Spatiotemporal Variability of Drought and Affected Croplands in the Horn of Africa." *Stochastic Environmental Research and Risk Assessment* 38, no. 1 (January 2024): 281–96. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00477-023-02575-1>.
- [6] Ali Warsame, Abdimalik, Jama Mohamed and Abdinur Ali Mohamed. "The Relationship between Environmental Degradation, Agricultural Crops, and Livestock Production in Somalia," August 31, 2022. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11356-022-22595-8>.
- [7] Bereketeab, Redie. *Intergovernmental Authority on Development: Internal Culture of Foreign Policymaking and Sources of Weaknesses*. Uppsala: Nordic Africa Institute, 2018.
- [8] Byiers, Bruce. "The Political Economy of Regional Integration in Africa; Intergovernmental Authority on Development Report." European center for development policy management (ECDPM), January 2016: 72. <http://ecdpm.org/peria/igad>.
- [9] Bizzotto, Paulina. "Understanding IGAD and CAADP," 2018:1-22. <http://www.ecdpm.org/pedr>
- [10] Byiers, Bruce. "Understanding Economic Integration, Peace, and Security in IGAD." *Political Economy Dynamics of Regional Organizations*, 2017.
- [11] Dersso, Solomon. "East Africa and the Intergovernmental Authority on Development." New York, USA: international Peace Institute, October 2014. https://www.ipinst.org/wp-content/uploads/publications/ipi_e_pub_igad.pdf.
- [12] Food and Agricultural organization of the Nations. "Drought in the Horn of Africa," 2022. 978-92-5-135622-7.
- [13] Fredu Nega Tegebu. "Climate Change-Induced Immigration in the Hron of Africa." South Africa: Africa portals, 2020.
- [14] Healy, Sally. *Hostage to Conflict: Prospects for Building Regional Economic Cooperation in the Horn of Africa*. A Chatham House Report. London: Royal Inst. of Intern. Affairs, Chatham House, 2011:1-53. ISBN 978-1-86203-256-9. www.chathamhouse.org
- [15] Henze, Paul B. *The Horn of Africa: From War to Peace*. London: Macmillan, 1991:1-247. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-349-21456-3>.
- [16] Isaac, Tseggai, and Andrew Targowski, eds. *African Civilization in the 21st Century*. Focus on Civilizations and Cultures. New York: Nova Publishers, 2015: 294. ISBN 978-1-63463-636-0 978-1-63463-637-7.
- [17] Mkutu, Kennedy. "Pastoralism and Conflict in the Horn of Africa." Bradford, UK: Africa Peace Forum/Safer world/University of Bradford, 2001:45. ISBN 0 948546 84 0.
- [18] Meier, Patrick, Doug Bond, and Joe Bond. "Environmental Influences on Pastoral Conflict in the Horn of Africa." *Political Geography* 26, no. 6 (August 2007): 716–35. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.polgeo.2007.06.001>.
- [19] Mulugeta, Gebrehiwot Berhe and Jean-Bosco Butera. *Climate Change and Pastoralism: Traditional Coping Mechanisms and Conflict in the Horn of Africa*. Institute for Peace and Security Studies, 2012. 978 9977 925 769.
- [20] Pradip Kumar Maurya, Sk Ajim Ali, Ateeque Ahmad, Qiaoqiao Zhou, Jonatas da Silva Castro, Ezzat Khan, and Hazrat Ali: "An Introduction to Environmental Degradation: Causes, Consequence and Mitigation," n.d. <https://doi.org/10.26832>.
- [21] Solomona, Negasi, c, Emiru Birhanea, b, Christopher Gordon, Mebrahtu Hailea, Fatemeh Taherid, and Hossein Azadie, f, *, Jürgen Scheffrang. "Environmental Impacts and Causes of Conflict in the Horn of Africa: A Review," 2018. <https://doi.org/10.1016>.
- [22] Heally, Sally. "Seeking Peace and Security in the Horn of Africa: The Contribution of the Inter-Governmental Authority on Development" Vol. 87, No. 1 (January 2011) (2011): 105–20. <https://doi.org/0020-5850>.
- [23] Dersso, Solomon. "East Africa and Intergovernmental Authority for Development." International Peace Institute, October 2014:1-15. https://www.ipinst.org/wp-content/uploads/publications/ipi_e_pub_igad.pdf
- [24] Burgess, Stephen F. "Stabilization, Peacebuilding, and Sustainability in the Horn of Africa." Air

University Press Vol. 3, No. 1 (Spring 2009): 81–118. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/10.2307/26268919>.

[25] Tafesse, Olika. "Conflicts and Conflict Resolution in the Horn of Africa: Toward the Study of Regional Peace and Security." Institute of Political Science of the University of Leipzig, 2009.

[26] Weldesellassie, K Isaac. "IGAD as an International Organization, Its Institutional Development and Shortcomings." *Journal of African Law* 55, no. 1 (April 2011): 1–29. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0021855311000015>.

[27] Yeboua, Kouassi and Cilliers, Jakkie. "Development Prospects for the Horn of Africa Countries to 2040." Institute For Security Studies, 2021:67. ISSN 2617-8133

